

Thematic Digital Competence Centers

Application form

1. General information

1a. Project title

Synthetic data: leveraging the potential of sensitive data in SSH research

1b. Relevant Thematic DCC Domain

- Life Sciences and Health (LSH)
 Natural and Engineering Sciences (NES)
 Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH)

1c. Project duration

24 months

1d. Responsible institution(s) and department

DANS, Data Section
 Maastricht University, Institute of Data Science
 Utrecht University, Department of Methodology & Statistics
 SURF, Innovation, Technology Exploration

1e. Lead applicant and co-applicants

Title, first name, initials, surname	Affiliation	Department	Role(s)
Erik-Jan van Kesteren	UU	Department of Methodology & Statistics	Lead applicant
Tim Kok	SURF	Innovation, Technology Exploration	Co-applicant
Giuseppe Gianquitto	SURF	Innovation, Technology Exploration	Co-applicant
Freek Dijkstra	SURF	Innovation, Technology Exploration	Co-applicant
Chang Sun	UM	Institute of Data Science, Faculty of Science and Engineering	Co-applicant
Ricarda Braukmann	DANS	Data Section	Co-applicant
Wim Hugo	DANS	CTO	Co-applicant

1f. Keywords

Synthetic Data, Privacy, Privacy-Enhancing Technologies, Research Infrastructure, Data Management.

1g. Disciplines

	Discipline:
Main discipline:	40.60.00 Psychometrics
Other disciplines (if applicable)	11.60.00 Probability theory, statistics
	37.90.00 Computers and the humanities, other
	38.10.00 Microeconomics

1h. Abstract (max. 500 words)

Many research questions in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) can be answered only through analysis of sensitive data. Rightfully, access to this data is often limited to protect copyright or the privacy of data subjects, making it challenging and cumbersome to use this data in research. Synthetic data can be a viable alternative to sensitive data for full or preliminary analyses and offers a way to improve analysis pipelines for researchers working with sensitive data, thereby supporting its FAIRness.

Through this project, we aim to increase the knowledge and application of synthetic data in the SSH community through accessible tools, training, and use-cases. We will focus on two existing solutions representing both extremes of the privacy-utility trade-off:

- The first tool, metasyn, takes a privacy-first approach to synthesizing tabular data which makes it easy to openly publish a mock dataset based on original sensitive data. Whilst the synthetic data generated with this tool cannot be used for a final analysis, it can be used to develop an initial analysis prior to, for example, a full analysis in a trusted research environment. This expedites the research workflow because it is easier to check if a dataset is suitable to answer a research question, and it allows a researcher to develop the analysis outside a fenced-off trusted research environment.
- The second solution, differentially private CGANs, leverages deep learning-based generative models to produce high-utility synthetic data that can support various applications, including data augmentation, analysis simulations, and model building. In this solution, we aim to address both structured (tabular) and unstructured (text) data, ideally enabling analyses without requiring the use of the original sensitive dataset. We acknowledge that such use of synthetic data introduces potential challenges, including introducing biases and privacy risks, which we investigate in addition to exploring mitigation strategies. Furthermore, we aim to shed light on the practical limits of synthetic data's utility and privacy, and provide insights on how to tune the privacy-utility trade-off for use cases in SSH.

These two solutions will be tailored to suit the needs of the SSH community and published as open-source tools (WP1). We will integrate the tooling into the DANS Data Station SSH – a Dataverse-based repository – to make it available in data publishing workflows (WP2). Through use-cases and collaboration with privacy officers, we will provide examples and guidelines for data providers about privacy and legal aspects (WP3, WP4). Finally, we will develop awareness and expertise by organizing workshops and presenting at community events (WP5).

1i. Public project title and public summary

NL

Synthetische data: bevordering van het gebruik van gevoelige gegevens in SSH-onderzoek

Synthetische data is een dataset met (min of meer) dezelfde eigenschappen als een oorspronkelijke dataset maar zonder privacygevoelige gegevens. Door synthetische data beschikbaar te maken in plaats van (of voorafgaand aan) de werkelijke dataset, krijgen wetenschappers sneller en makkelijker toegang tot vertrouwelijke data. In dit project worden twee tools voor het maken van synthetische data ingezet om bestaande datasets te ontsluiten, waaronder datasets die bij DANS zijn opgeslagen.

ENG

Synthetic data: leveraging the potential of sensitive data in SSH research

Synthetic data is a dataset with (more or less) the same properties as an original dataset but without privacy-sensitive information. By making synthetic data available instead of (or prior to) the actual dataset, scientists gain faster and easier access to confidential data. In this project, two tools for creating synthetic data are used to unlock existing datasets, including datasets archived at DANS.

2. Project information

2.1 Involvement of TDCC domain in drafting application (max. 400 words)

Right from the beginning, the project was set up to have a large involvement of participants and stakeholders from the SSH domain. The project proposal participants included two research universities (UM, UU) active in the SSH domain and two national infrastructure service providers (DANS, SURF). The team members have several direct and indirect links to SSH Research Infrastructures CLARIAH and ODISSEI. The project members are also active in other communities that are well-connected with the SSH community such as Health-RI, ICT.OPEN, and GOFAIR.

Both this network and the consultation provided through the TDCC-SSH process was used to gather input on the project idea and to ensure its relevance to the SSH domain. The use cases listed in this proposal were established using input from the community.

In preparing our project proposal, we sought input from the TDCC teams at the earliest stages to align well with the TDCC SSH roadmap. On 2 May 2024, the project proposal was presented as part of the TDCC-SSH submission process, where the SSH community were invited to give input on the proposal. The feedback gained from these sessions has directly shaped this current proposal.

Relationship to and coordination with SSHOC-NL activities

The partners involved are closely connected to ODISSEI and CLARIAH, the two Dutch infrastructures involved in the SSHOC-NL project. SSHOC-NL also focuses on improving FAIRness and scientific infrastructure for the SSH domain by connecting and further developing the services and tools already available within ODISSEI and CLARIAH. The goal of SSHOC-NL and this project are very much aligned, yet, within SSHOC-NL there is no dedicated work on synthetic data.

We want to use the connections to SSHOC-NL to boost the impact of our work. We plan to seek alignment with the expertise workstream in the SSHOC-NL project for community outreach and to receive feedback on our project. We also plan to collaborate with their Ethical Legal Social Implications (ELSI) helpdesk in WP4. Furthermore, the tools from this project could be listed in the SSHOC-NL tools registry (CLARIAH Ineo). Through the publication of synthetic datasets at DANS, their metadata is automatically ingested into the ODISSEI Portal. SSHOC-NL may also provide opportunities for the sustainability of our deliverables beyond the lifetime of this project, and we plan to initiate discussions about this sustainability early in the project.

2.2 Roadmap ambition/activity cluster/challenge

NES	SSH	LSH
<input type="checkbox"/> FAIR data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> FAIRification of data and software	<input type="checkbox"/> Strengthen good data stewardship and harmonise data access practises
<input type="checkbox"/> Sustainable software and e-science	<input type="checkbox"/> Raising awareness	<input type="checkbox"/> Enhance the interoperability of digital solutions and resources
<input type="checkbox"/> Connections to the international activities	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Knowledge enhancement	<input type="checkbox"/> Strengthen the capacity and expertise base in digital research
<input type="checkbox"/> Long-term data archiving	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Addressing pressing issues	
<input type="checkbox"/> Locate computing capacity close to the storage	<input type="checkbox"/> Building a network	
<input type="checkbox"/> Human capital		
<input type="checkbox"/> Cross-field collaborations		

2.3 Relevance (max. 400 words)

Alignment with TDCC roadmaps and ambitions

This project aligns closely with the TDCC-SSH roadmap and ambitions, targeting three key activity clusters: FAIRification of data and software, Knowledge enhancement, and Addressing pressing issues; and four challenges: Expertise, Support, Sensitive data, and FAIR data and software. We will elaborate on the activity clusters and challenges in the discussion of the project's impact below.

Urgency and timeliness

The project addresses the pressing need of SSH researchers to access sensitive data in a secure, yet efficient manner. By reducing access barriers to sensitive data, the project will unlock new avenues for SSH research and contribute to broader digitalisation efforts within the SSH domain.

Impact

Digitalisation

The project will foster 1) expertise development by organising workshops that will equip researchers, data owners, and data stewards with the knowledge to apply synthetic data solutions; and 2) supporting infrastructures through participation from DANS and SURF, and a collaboration with local DCCs and use case partners, which will ensure sustainable support for synthetic data.

FAIR principles

Synthetic data has the potential to improve the FAIRness of sensitive data in the following ways.

Accessibility

In the case of high-utility synthetic data, previously restricted data can be made accessible to a larger group of researchers. DUO, for example, made statistically representative synthetic data of their education data available to researchers.

Interoperability

Synthetic data provides representative data that researchers can use to test the integration of the sensitive data with other data, as well as how the data can interoperate with software and analysis workflows. Moreover, our privacy-first synthetic data tool, metasynt, uses a metadata standard that can further improve the interoperability of sensitive data. One of the goals of this project is to expand the data types supported by metasynt, as well as provide tooling to generate free text data (see WP1).

Reusability

Synthetic data makes it easier for researchers to (re)use sensitive data made available in a restricted trusted research environment (TRE), such as SANE and CBS-RA, by making a privacy-friendly version of the data available that can be used to develop a reproducible analysis before accessing an (expensive) TRE.

In addition, the software and infrastructure solutions developed in this project will be made FAIR, and through our use cases we intend to make actual sensitive datasets accessible to researchers.

2.4 Project outline including work packages (max. 1600 words)

The project is divided into five work packages, which will be worked on in parallel for the duration of 2 years. All packages depend on the tools developed in WP1. We do not anticipate this to lead to delays because existing versions of the tools can be used in the earlier phases of WP2 and WP3. Moreover, the tasks in WP2 and WP3 will provide input for the development in WP1, so these activities can and should be worked on simultaneously. The outreach task in WP5 is expected to start in the second half of the project.

The table below presents an overview of the different work packages. The main tasks of each work package are discussed below.

Work package	Contributors	Deliverables	Dependencies
WP1: SSH synthetic data generation tools	UU (Lead T1.1), UM (Lead T1.2)	Open source software Reports and/or scientific papers	WP3
WP2: Integrating synthetic data tools in data repositories	DANS (Lead T2.1 and T2.2), SURF (Support)	Documentation Prototype Evaluation of service integration	WP1
WP3: Synthetic data use cases in the SSH domain	UU (Lead T3.1), UM (Lead T3.2)	Synthetic data products Reports	WP1
WP4: Privacy and legal aspects of synthetic data	UU (Lead T4.1), SURF (Lead T4.2)	Report/guideline Workshop proposal	WP3
WP5: Outreach and Project Management	All (SURF in lead)	Dissemination of work Events	WP1-4

Work packages

WP1: SSH synthetic data generation tools.

WP1 will develop and improve open-source synthetic data generation tools for SSH data. Guided by the use-cases in WP3, the goal is to provide two tools which reduce data access barriers for sensitive SSH datasets: a privacy-focused tool aimed at data containing personal, medical, or other highly sensitive data (T1.1), and an utility-focused synthetic data tool aimed at enabling researchers to perform analyses on datasets which require fewer privacy constraints (T1.2).

Task 1.1: Privacy-first synthetic data generation.

T1.1 will further the development of metasynt, a software package to generate synthetic data in a privacy-friendly way (Schram, Spithorst, & Van Kesteren, under review). While this focus on privacy limits the statistical validity, the generated data allows scientists to make their research more reproducible and enables data owners to make their datasets FAIR while minimising disclosure risks (Van Kesteren, in press).

While metasynt has reached a relatively stable state, additional work is required to meet the needs of SSH researchers. Examples are support for several common data types in the SSH domain, such as answers to open questions and dates and times for longitudinal studies, and specific constraints on the synthetic data, such as enforcing starting dates to come before end dates. To prioritise the new features, this task will closely collaborate with the WP3 use-cases. In addition, metasynt's metadata format will be improved to integrate with data repositories (part of WP2).

Task 1.2: High-utility synthetic data generation.

T1.2 focuses on generating two types of high-utility synthetic data: 1) structured (tabular) data; and 2) unstructured (text) data. This synthetic data has similar variable distributions and correlations as the original data or maintains semantic coherence and contextual relevance in the case of unstructured text. First, we will extend the differential privacy conditional generative adversarial network model (DP-CGANS, Sun, C., et. al., 2023) for structured data in the SSH domain. Second, we will create a text generator with a certain level of privacy preservation which takes structured data (tabular and graph data) as input. Additionally, we will advance metrics for assessing the data's utility and risk of privacy leakage. We believe that through transparent reporting and best practices, we can guide SSH researchers on the appropriate application of such advanced synthetic data methods.

WP2: Integrating synthetic data tools in data repositories

The aim of WP2 is to assess how the tools from WP1 could be offered through data repositories by creating synthetic versions of datasets available in the repository. We take the DANS Data Station SSH as an example use case. On this

Data Station, many depositors restrict access to the original data. A synthetic derivative which preserves privacy could be made available more openly. WP2 focuses on the integration of metasyn, although we will also assess use cases for DP-CGANS.

Since the Data Station is based on Dataverse software, integrations we achieve can be used by other Dataverse-based repositories, including many Dutch university repositories. We plan to align this work with standards for connecting tools and repositories developed in European projects (EOSC EDEN; EOSC Data Commons) and SSHOC-NL.

WP2 considers two scenarios separated in two tasks. The scenarios are expected to be documented and implemented as prototypes on existing services at DANS and/or SURF.

Task 2.1: Creating synthetic data as part of the deposit pipeline

T2.1 will assess how the tools from WP1 could be integrated into the predeposit pipeline. In this phase, a user provides information about the dataset to be deposited and they should be able to invoke tools to preprocess the dataset (i.e. create a synthetic derivative). We will also consider the requirement that some data owners may prefer to process their datasets locally and only archive the synthetic derivative.

Task 2.2: Creating synthetic data from existing datasets

T2.2 will assess the scenario in which users can request a synthetic dataset from a published dataset, after approval by the data owner. Datasets that meet the criteria for the WP1 tools will be labelled and a process to invoke the tools to create a synthetic derivative will be implemented.

WP3: Synthetic data use cases in the SSH domain

The goal of WP3 is to apply the tools developed in WP1 to use cases relevant to the SSH domain. Each type of tool has its own task. Below we list the use cases.

Task 3.1: Use-cases privacy-first approach

- YOUth collected a large dataset on child development and wants to make their data easily accessible for research. To reduce access barriers, we will collaborate on producing low-utility synthetic data for their sensitive questionnaire data.
- FIRMBACKBONE collected company data, wants to make their data easily accessible, and is also a use-case for SANE (secure analysis environment, a PDI-SSH project). Together, we will pilot the integration of easily available synthetic data in their infrastructure.
- Statistics Netherlands (CBS) enables scientists to analyze their microdata using a secure remote access (RA) environment. In cooperation with CBS, we will investigate whether and how it is possible for researchers to offer aggregated, guidelines-compliant output using metasyn in order to generate synthetic data outside the RA environment with low utility. As part of this process, synthetic data files are rigorously checked by experienced output controllers to ensure no disclosure actually takes place. Driven by this use-case, CBS will also consider how to deal with these types of synthetic datasets legally and in terms of communication (see WP4), ideally resulting in updated guidelines.

Task 3.2: Use-cases high-utility approach

- DUO collects education data in the Netherlands. They have previously published synthetic data using Synthpop. We will collaborate with DUO to apply different tabular data generators (DP-CGANS, CTGAN), conduct downstream analysis tasks, and evaluate the utility and privacy of synthetic data. We will also work on a guideline for best practices and limitations, covering technical and legal aspects.
- GPT-NL is building a Dutch open language model that is transparent, fair and verifiable. Together we will use synthetic data to enlarge GPT-NL's training corpus, thereby making it useful for SSH researchers. We plan to generate synthetic text data based on structured data such as tabular and graph data from SSH data providers (e.g., Nationaal Archief). We will conduct quality checks to assess potential performance degradation caused by synthetic data.
- The National Library (KB) has a large collection of Dutch publications, but researchers face challenges to access this corpus due to copyright restrictions. Through experiments, we will explore whether synthetic data tools can create non-copyrighted textual data from existing published text, as well as whether the output can be used by researchers in the humanities.

WP4: Privacy and legal aspects of synthetic data.

WP4 aims to engage ethical and legal experts to create guidelines on the privacy and legal aspects of implementing synthetic data solutions.

Task 4.1: Create recommendations and guidelines for data providers on the privacy and legal aspects of implementing synthetic data solutions

The goal of T4.1 is to engage ethical-legal experts from academia and our use case partners from WP3 together with technical researchers in synthetic data to jointly make recommendations and guidelines for the broader SSH community to implement synthetic data in a responsible manner based on the lessons learned in this project.

Task 4.2: Organise a workshop to engage ethical-legal experts

We will submit a proposal to NWO's Lorentz Center for a workshop in the second half of the project to gather ethical-legal experts from the Netherlands who are interested in privacy issues in synthetic data. The expected outcomes are creating 1) collaborations between technical and legal experts in synthetic data topics; 2) a network of legal experts who are working on synthetic data; and 3) a guideline for implementing and using synthetic data. If our workshop proposal is not accepted, we will organize a (smaller) workshop targeting a similar audience as part of WP5.

WP5: Outreach and Project Management

WP5 concerns the dissemination of the deliverables and findings from the other work packages and the project management.

Task 5.1: Outreach

- Create and teach workshops on synthetic data in general and publishing sensitive datasets in particular.
- Support and attract new users by participating in open science conferences, SURF Research Day, etc.
- Offer consultancy to others in the community who would like to apply either method of synthetic data tooling themselves.

Task 5.2: Project Management

T5.2 will monitor the quality of the different work packages in this project, promote timely alignment of the separate work packages with one another, and maintain close connections between this project and the broader SSH research community initiatives such as those in SSHOC-NL.

References

Schram, R. D., Spithorst, S., & Van Kesteren, E.-J. (Under Review). Metasyn: Transparent Generation of Synthetic Tabular Data with Privacy Guarantees. *Journal of Open Source Software*.

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Sun, C., van Soest, J., Dumontier, M. (2023). Generating synthetic personal health data using conditional generative adversarial networks combining with differential privacy. *Journal of Biomedical Informatics*.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbi.2023.104404>

Van Kesteren, E.-J. (2024). To democratize research with sensitive data, we should make synthetic data more accessible. *Patterns* 5(9) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2024.101058>

3. Declarations and signature

Funding elsewhere

Have you requested funding for this project elsewhere?

No

Yes

By submitting this form, I declare that:

- I have completed this form truthfully;
- I meet the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the [Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity 2018](#);

Initial(s) and surname(s): E van Kesteren

Place: Utrecht

Date: **13/11/2024**